

PHARMAAYURVED ONLINE RESEARCH JOURNAL FOR PHARMACY, AYURVED AND ALLIED SCIENCES

<http://www.pharmaayurved.in/>

POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION – INGREDIENTS OF *KATUCHATURJATAKA*

1. Raju Zinzala, Third year P.G. Scholar, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India
2. Dharmendra Jani, Associate Professor, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India
3. Isha Adhyaru, Lab Technician, Upgraded P.G. Department of *Dravyaguna*, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat, India

Article Received on: 04-06-24

Accepted on: 07-06-24

Published on: 15-06-24

Abstract

Background: Material & Method: Powder microscopy of *Katuchaturjataka* was carried out. *Katuchaturjataka* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.) and *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.). Slides of each ingredient of *Katuchaturjataka* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Katuchaturjataka* shows Pearl gland, glandular trichomes, Fibers, vessels, starch grains, pitted vessels, phloem Fibers etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** One of the simplest techniques for accurately identifying a herbal medicine is powder microscopy. Structures like prismatic crystals, parenchymatous cell, are indicating presence of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton); phloem fiber, phloem parenchyma etc. are indicating presence of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl); pearl gland, schizogenous mucilaginous canal, glandular & non glandular trichomes etc. are indicating presence of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.); hyaline layer, beaker cells etc. are indicating presence of *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.) in the *Katuchaturjataka*.

For Corresponds:

Name of Author: Dr. Raju Zinzala

Email: ahirraju10@gmail.com

Key Words:

Powder microscopy, *Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton, *Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm., *Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl, *Piper nigrum* Linn.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the global market has seen a rise in the use of natural treatments. All sectors of the pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical, nutraceutical, etc. businesses use a lot of herbal treatments. The growing demand for herbal treatments has led to a situation where pharmaceutical companies and dealers often observe substitution and adulteration. Pharmacognosy is therefore essential for monitoring and guaranteeing the best possible therapeutic efficacy. Powder microscopy, a subfield of pharmacognosy, is the simplest, most economical, and most straightforward way to standardize and authenticate herbal medications.

The key to attaining maximum therapeutic efficacy is to use the exact herbal medicines prescribed by the scriptures. It cannot be changed in any way to get the desired result. As a result, powder microscopy is essential for identifying and locating contaminants in herbal medications. Here, for the present study *Katuchaturjataka* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Katuchaturjataka* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved.¹ It contains *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton, Family - Scitaminae), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl, Family - Lauraceae), *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm., Family - Lauraceae) and *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn., Family - Piperaceae).

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Katuchaturjataka*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features in the powder of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.) and *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.).
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Katuchaturjataka was used for the powder microscopy. *Katuchaturjataka* is an ayurvedic formulation containing *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.), and *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.). Seeds of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton), stembark of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl), leaf of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.) and fruits of *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of *Katuchaturjataka* were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.²⁻⁵

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No.1: Powder microscopic characters found in *Katuchaturjataka*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Ela</i>	<i>Twaka</i>	<i>Patra</i>	<i>Maricha</i>
1.	Prismatic crystals	+			
2.	Parenchymatous cell	+			

3.	Fiber	+		+	
4.	Epidermal cells	+			
5.	Acicular crystal	+			
6.	Starch grains	+	+		
7.	Sclerenchyma of testa	+			
8.	Pitted vessel		+		
9.	Phloem Fiber		+		
10.	Phloem parenchyma		+		
11.	Parenchyma containing small acicular raphides		+		
12.	Scleroids		+		
13.	Pearl gland			+	
14.	Thick-walled cell of upper epidermis			+	
15.	Vessel			+	
16.	Schizogenous mucilaginous canal			+	
17.	Glandular Trichomes			+	
18.	Non-glandular Trichomes			+	
19.	Hyaline layer				+
20.	Beaker cells				+
21.	Spiral vessels				+
22.	Volatile oil cell				+
23.	Pigment layer				+
24.	Epicarp cells				+

Table No.2: Powder microscopic study of *Ela (Elettaria cardemomum (Linn.) Maton)*

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ela</i>	Figure no.
1.	Prismatic crystals	01
2.	Parenchymatous cell	02, 07
3.	Fiber	03
4.	Epidermal cells	04

5.	Acicular crystal	05
6.	Starch grains	06
7.	Sclerenchyma of testa	08

Table No.3: Powder microscopic study of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Twaka</i>	Figure no.
1.	Starch grain	
2.	Pitted vessel	
3.	Phloem Fiber	
4.	Phloem parenchyma	
5.	Parenchyma containing small acicular raphides	
6.	Scleroids	

Table No.4: Powder microscopic study of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Patra</i>	Figure no.
1.	Fiber	09
2.	Pearl gland	10
3.	Thick-walled cell of upper epidermis	11
4.	Vessel	12
5.	Schizogenous mucilaginous canal	13
6.	Glandular Trichomes	14
7.	Non-glandular Trichomes	15

Table No.5: Powder microscopic study of *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Maricha</i>	Figure no.
1.	Hyaline layer	21
2.	Beaker cells	22,25
3.	Spiral vessels	23

4.	Volatile oil cell	24
5.	Pigment layer	26
6.	Epicarp cells	27

The current study provides knowledge on the microscopic characteristics of the herbal materials. The powder of *Katuchaturjataka* was chosen for this microscopic investigation. Powder microscopy of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton) shows, prismatic crystals, parenchymatous cell, fiber, epidermal cells, acicular crystal, starch grains, sclerenchyma of testa. Powder microscopy of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl) shows, starch grain, pitted vessel, phloem fiber, phloem parenchyma, parenchyma containing small acicular raphides, scleroids. Powder microscopy of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.) shows, fiber, pearl gland, thick-walled cell of upper epidermis, vessel, schizogenous mucilaginous canal, glandular trichomes, non-glandular trichomes. Powder microscopy of *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.) shows, hyaline layer, beaker cells, spiral vessels, volatile oil cell, pigment layer, epicarp cells.

The process of standardizing Ayurvedic formulation is complex and difficult. However, it is imperative to ensure the effectiveness and safety of herbal remedies, making them appropriate for their application. In the current experiment, every powder component of *Katuchaturjataka* was inspected under a microscope and its microscopic properties were noted. These qualities might be helpful in accurately recognizing and detecting impurities in goods that are sold.

Powder microscopy of *Elettaria cardemomum*

Fig.01

Fig.02

Fig.03

Fig.04

Fig.05

Fig.06

Fig.07

Fig.08

Powder microscopy of *Cinnamomum Tamala*

Fiber

Fig.09

Pearl gland

Fig.10

Thick-walled cell of upper epidermis

Schizogenous mucilaginous canal

Fig.11

Vessel

Fig.12

Fig.13

Glandular Trichomes

Fig.14

Non-glandular Trichomes

Fig.15

Powder microscopy of *Cinnamomum verum*

Fig.16

Fig.17

Fig.18

Fig.19

Fig.20

Powder microscopy of *Piper nigrum*

Fig.21

Hyaline layer
Beaker cells

Fig.22

Fig.23

Spiral vessels
Volatile oil cell

Fig.24

Fig.25

Beaker cell
Pigment layer

Fig.26

Fig.27

Epicarp cells

CONCLUSION:

The current study's findings aid in the identification of herbal formulations like *Katuchaturjataka*. Prismatic crystals, parenchymatous cell, fiber, epidermal cells, acicular crystal, starch grains, sclerenchyma of testa these structures are indicating presence of *Ela* (*Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton); starch grain, pitted vessel, phloem fiber, phloem parenchyma, small acicular raphides, scleroids these structures are indicating presence of *Twaka* (*Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl); fiber, pearl gland, thick-walled cell of upper epidermis, vessel, schizogenous mucilaginous canal, glandular & non glandular trichomes these structures are indicating presence of *Patra* (*Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. -Ham.) Nees & Eberm.); hyaline layer, beaker cells, spiral vessels, volatile oil cell, pigment layer, epicarp cells these structures are indicating presence of *Maricha* (*Piper nigrum* Linn.) in the *Katuchaturjataka*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors are thankful to Department of AYUSH, principal of Government Ayurved College, teachers and students of PG unit and Co-worker of GAC, Vadodara for their cordial support.

REFERENCES

1. Narhari pandit, Raja Nighantu, edited by Dr. Satish Chandra Sankhyadhar, Dr. Deepika Sankhyakadhar, forward by Prof. K.C. Chuneekar. Mishrakadi Varga, Ver. 19. Reprint edition, Varanasi: Chowkhambha ~~India~~, 2017. P.no. 1064
2. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Elettaria cardemomum* (Linn.) Maton., Vol 1, ICMR, New Delhi, 2003, p. 95.
3. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Cinamomum verum* J.S. Presl., Vol 1, ICMR, New Delhi, 2003, p. 74.
4. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Cinamomum tamala* (Buch. - Ham.) Nees & Eberm., Vol 3, ICMR, New Delhi, 2003, p. 149.
5. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Piper nigrum* Linn., Vol 8, ICMR, New Delhi, 2010, p. 255.